

AN OVERVIEW OF DIVING, SALVAGE,
OFFSHORE POLLUTION ABATEMENT, AND UNDERWATER
SHIP MAINTENANCE

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SUMMARY

This paper will address major technical and equipment developments during the past ten years in U. S. Navy diving, salvage, offshore pollution abatement and underwater ship maintenance programs. The scope of the paper is, of necessity, limited to general accomplishments.

DIVING

The diving program has experienced a strong growth over the last ten years, both in equipment development and testing as well as hyperbaric medicine. Whereas the Navy was once the leader in diving, the commercial sector, due to the stimulus of the offshore oil industry, must now be considered to be in the forefront. This is not to say that the Navy has not progressed; it has however shifted its focus to those particular problems associated with military diving operations. The Navy diving program has encompassed new equipment development, enhancement of the capabilities of the Navy Experimental Diving Unit and the establishment of a strong diving systems certification program.

DIVING EQUIPMENTS

Mark V Deep Sea Diving Outfit

The MK V deep sea rig has served the Navy for over half a century and will long be remembered by Navy divers as an old friend that provided them with a unique and complete capability to perform underwater work. This diving system is now being retired from Navy service.

Mark 12 Surface Supplied Diving System

Acquisition of the final sets of this system in 1984 will provide Navy diving activities with state-of-the-art surface supplied diving equipment. The MARK 12 system provides the Navy diver more mobility, increased safety, better visibility, and an enhanced life support system. The mixed gas version, currently entering the production phase, will provide these same qualities plus extending the diving depth from 200 to 300 FSW. The prototype rigs have been used operationally and have received high marks for performance from the Fleet diver.

Mark 1 Surface Supplied Diving System

This demand, as opposed to open circuit, diving system has been in fleet usage for the past seven years. This system, patterned after the KIRBY MORGAN Band Mask, was developed as a replacement for the old Jack Browne rig. It is a lightweight rig capable of operating in depths to 190 FSW on air or 300 FSW on mixed gas. The rig has proven to be extremely useful, particularly for inspection and underwater maintenance type work.

Mark 14 Saturation Diving System

The MK 14 is currently undergoing test and evaluation with production expected to start in late 1984. This system is best described as a closed circuit or push-pull saturation diving system that will enable

the Navy to perform highly efficient diving operations to a depth of 850 FSW. The push-pull feature of the system will enable the helium used by the diver to be reclaimed and reused thereby sharply reducing helium logistic requirements and enabling the conduct of longer duration saturation diving operations. This system is slated for installation in the MK 2 diving systems in the ASR-21 Class submarine rescue ships.

Standard Navy Diving Boat

Fleet divers have long expressed a need for a standardized Navy diving boat in order to conduct the myriad of diving tasks assigned to diving activities such as tenders, naval station diving lockers, and naval shipyards. The design of the boat, which incorporates a portable diving module in a standard 50-foot Navy work boat, has been completed. A contract for prototype construction was awarded in 1982, however contractual difficulties have delayed completion of the boat. When completed, in late 1983, the boat will provide the working diver a surface supplied diving capability to 190 FSW. Both the MK 12 and MK 1 diving systems will be accommodated as well as SCUBA. In addition, the boat will provide shop spaces, welding equipment, shallow water mooring capability, and equipment handling facilities as well as modest living accommodations. The portability of the diving module will enable the boat and diving system to be loaded on board tenders and repair ships for utilization in forward deployed areas.

Navy Experimental Diving Unit (NEDU)

During the mid-1970's, NEDU moved from its historic location at the Washington Navy Yard to Panama City, Florida.

NEDU is composed of two major diving complexes - the Ocean Simulation Facility and the Experimental Diving Facility.

The Ocean Simulation Facility, the largest of its kind in the world, consists of a large wet pot and five dry chambers. The facility is capable of achieving depths of up to 2000 FSW and temperature ranges of 29° F to 85° F. The wet pot can accommodate all types of diving systems as well as small manned submersibles. All of NEDU's manned tests are accomplished in this system. The Experimental Diving Facility is smaller and is essentially used to conduct unmanned tests of diving equipments. One of NEDU's major accomplishments has been the conduct of a manned saturation dive to 1800 FSW in 1979. The future calls for NEDU to continue to develop diving procedures and equipment, evaluate and develop new diving tables and concentrate on the testing of all diving equipment destined for use by the Navy.

Diving System Certification

Undoubtedly the most significant influence on the Navy Diving Program during the past ten years has been the implementation of the diving systems certification program. This program seeks to ensure that Navy diving equipments and systems are the safest in the world. This is accomplished through systematic evaluation of equipment and system design, material

adequacy, fabrication and operation. To date the certification program encompasses some 250 systems and equipments ranging from shipboard and diving craft installations to individual surface supplied and SCUBA equipments.

SALVAGE

Contrasted to the diving program, the Navy Salvage program has experienced a decline over the last decade. The total number of salvage and towing ships as well as experienced personnel has been reduced. In the late 1970's however this trend was reversed and the future of the Salvage Navy now looks brighter than before. The experience of the Royal Navy during the Falklands War fully demonstrated the need for a viable salvage force. The Navy salvage program, as now constituted, will enable the U. S. Navy to have a strong salvage capability.

Emergency Ship Salvage Material (ESSM) System

The ESSM system is composed of a multitude of salvage equipments encompassing wire rope, anchors, chain, pumps, compressors, generators, winches, piping, etc. It serves as the primary equipment backup for the Navy's fleet salvage forces.

Prior to 1976, the ESSM system was composed of some sixteen salvage equipment bases located at naval shipyards and at overseas bases.

In 1976 these bases were consolidated into two U. S. bases and 3 overseas bases. Since 1978, the ESSM system has been undergoing a systematic upgrading through the deletion of obsolete equipment and procurement of modern salvage equipment. The most recent addition has been the procurement of the hydraulic puller. This machine, capable of a 50-ton line pull, will replace the old 8-ton beach gear winch and associated falls in the Navy's beach gear system. The machine will greatly simplify the installation and operation of a pulling system on the salvage ships. Future major endeavors to upgrade the ESSM system include the development of lightweight high capacity pumps, and offshore fire fighting equipment.

DEEP DRONE

In the mid-1970's it became increasingly apparent that there existed a need for the Navy to have a capability to inspect and identify objects and perform work at depths greater than that at which the diver could work. In 1976, the office of the Supervisor of Salvage was tasked to develop a remote unmanned tethered vehicle to perform such tasks. As a result, the Navy acquired the DEEP DRONE, a 2000-foot tethered vehicle with underwater television and still photography capabilities. The original DEEP DRONE performed beyond expectations. The system was easily transported, highly reliable, and capable of being installed on virtually any platform. The system has been upgraded over the years and is now capable of working at depths up to 5500 feet, has three television cameras, two manipulators, sonar, and underwater still photography capability. DEEP DRONE has continued to demonstrate exceptional reliability and has proven its worth in conducting underwater recovery operations, the most significant being the recovery of helicopter wreckage from a depth of 3200 feet.

Salvage Ships

In the early 1970's the inventory of salvage and towing ships consisted primarily of ships built prior to 1947. The only exception was the Edenton class fleet

salvage tug (ATS). This class of three ships was built in England and entered service in 1971. The mid-1970's brought the retirement of most of the fleet tugs (ATF) and several of the salvage rescue ships (ARS). These retirements were partially made up through the introduction, in 1979, of the seven Military Sealift Command (MSC)-operated Powhatan Class fleet tugs (T-ATF). These 7200 HP ships are based on the design of the offshore supply ship and have some salvage capability although nowhere near the capability of the ships they replaced. As it became apparent that a replacement for the aging salvage rescue ships (ARS) would be required, the Navy embarked on the ARS-50 Class acquisition program. This program currently calls for the construction of four 4200 HP ships. These ships are fully capable salvage ships and will form the backbone of the Navy's future salvage force. The first of the class is scheduled for delivery in late 1984.

OFFSHORE POLLUTION ABATEMENT

The Navy's pollution abatement program is composed of two segments: harbor pollution abatement under the cognizance of the Naval Facilities Engineering Command and offshore pollution abatement which is the responsibility of the Naval Sea Systems Command. This section will address only the offshore portion.

Since its inception, the objective of the Navy offshore pollution abatement program has been to provide a rapid, centrally managed response to possible Navy offshore oil spills on a worldwide basis. Responsibility for fulfillment of this objective was assigned to the Navy Supervisor of Salvage because that office was already structured to respond to Navy emergencies on the same basis.

Over the last decade, the program has built an extensive inventory of pollution abatement equipment and has participated in many offshore oil spill clean-up operations in response to requests from the U. S. Coast Guard. Fortunately, none of these operations have been the result of a Navy spill.

The present inventory of state of the art pollution abatement equipment can be considered second to none and is the result of extensive research, analysis, testing and procurement programs. Major components of the spill response system include skimmers, oil boom, boom mooring systems, and auxiliary support equipment.

The heart of the system is the offshore skimmer. The skimmer is a 36-foot self propelled boat with an inclined belt skimming system that can be operated in a self-propelled or towed mode. The most efficient method of collecting oil is in the towed mode. The skimmer is designed to operate in up to a state three sea.

Complementing the skimmer is a floating oil boom that can be used in either a stationary configuration to entrap and pool the oil for pickup or in a "V" configuration in conjunction with the skimmer. In this latter configuration the boom forms the towlines for a skimmer and serves to channel the oil into the skimmer's pick up system. The boom mooring system is composed of a mooring buoy, a 500 lb anchor, chain and up to 200 feet of nylon mooring line. Through the use of this mooring system, the boom can be positioned to take advantage of prevailing winds and currents to collect the spilled oil.

Auxiliary equipment includes oil bladders for retention of collected oil, 26-foot small craft for towing the skimmers, rigging and shop vans for on scene

mechanical support, and support vans for on scene communication and administrative support.

The above equipments have proved their ruggedness and versatility in several oil spill operations. The most significant of these occurred during the Bay of Campeche IXTOC I spill in 1979. During this six month cleanup operation, Navy equipment was deployed along the coast of Texas from Brownsville to Corpus Christi.

UNDERWATER SHIP MAINTENANCE

Underwater ship maintenance has long been a responsibility of the Navy diving community. In recent years, however, it has taken on greater importance due to higher fuel prices, fewer dry docking facilities, and the goal of the Navy to extend the interval between dry dockings from two or three years to five years.

Underwater Hull Cleaning

The major underwater maintenance program being undertaken by the Navy is the hull cleaning program. The impetus for this program is the need to save fuel in the face of high oil prices. As a result the Navy now cleans each ship on an average of three to four times between drydocking periods. This is accomplished through the use of multibrush hull cleaning machines that travel the length of the ship and scrape off the underwater growth and barnacles. In those areas in which the machine can't be used, divers employ single brush scrubbers to clean the hull. This program has resulted in an estimated 10% annual savings in fuel costs. An additional benefit from this program has been an increased frequency in hull inspections which has served to highlight other hull maintenance problems such as pitting, blistered paint, etc., at an earlier stage in their development.

Non-Destructive Testing

Closely associated with the hull cleaning program is the non-destructive testing program. To date this program encompasses underwater ultrasonic and magnetic particle testing and stereo photography techniques. Utilization of these techniques have great potential for identifying thinned areas of a ship's hull that may require replacement during overhaul and in identifying the extent of possible cracks in rudders and hull plating in order to effect permanent waterborne repair.

Waterborne Repair

Aligned with the above endeavors is the effort of the Navy to develop techniques and equipments to aid the diver in making underwater repairs. Such effort includes underwater welding, underwater painting, cofferdam design and construction, under hull work platforms, hull skin valve replacement, and propeller removal and handling equipments. The potential of this program for savings in both time and dollars is one that must be exploited in the future if the Navy is to derive full benefit from one of its most valuable assets - the Navy Diver.